

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NEED TO CHANGE APPROACHES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING

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The dynamism of the changes taking place in the modern world (Figure 1) has necessitated a rethinking of the fundamental principles of the functioning of the world's education systems. In a rapidly changing world, the first, key question for educational policy makers, schools in general, and teachers in particular, the question is: "What is to be learned by students in the 21st century?" and second, no less significant "How will teachers prepare students for the 21st century?"

**Globalisation Demographic changes Technology Sustainable
development Peace and Security**

Figure 1. Interdependence of changes in world processes

Currently, in the field of education, the equal importance of the processes of formation of students' relevant knowledge and relevant practical skills is generally recognized. The fundamental difference between modern teaching and learning processes is their priority in the formation of students' readiness for the practical use of existing knowledge, in addition to formal possession of them, which is more consistent with the essence of skills in demand in the 21st century.

Teachers should have sufficient time, demonstrate competence not only in the development of students' knowledge and skills, but also in their personal development, taking into account the importance of individualization of learning and the formation of students' meta-consciousness - skills of learning how to learn (Schleicher, 2012) . Without any doubt pedagogical sphere demands:

Teachers need a diverse arsenal of learning strategies, providing them with opportunities to combine various pedagogical approaches, as well as knowing the answers to one of the key questions:

How and in what situations is it possible to achieve the effectiveness of using each specific method and strategy?

- The strategies used by teachers relate to the issues of teaching the whole class as a whole, as well as the content orientation of the implemented research, group work, independent work of students. At the same time, educational strategies of teachers should not exclude the personal feedback of each student.

- Teachers should have a sufficiently thorough knowledge of how learning takes place, about the level of motivation of individual students, about the emotions they experience and about their life outside of school.

- Teachers should be able to cooperate not only with colleagues in the subject they teach, but also in other academic subjects; with representatives of one organization and a number of other organizations; within the framework of network professional communities and various partnership agreements involving the active use of coaching processes and mentoring.

- Teachers should have solid skills in the field of information technology and methods of their use as an effective teaching tool, in particular, skills in digital resources, as well as an automated system for managing the teaching process in order to track the learning process of students.
- Teachers should improve their potential professional abilities to collaborate with colleagues and participate in the development, management and planning of the learning environment.
- Last but not least, teachers need to reflect continuously in the course of his practice in order to learn from his experience.

Learner skills that are relevant in the 21st century are not new. For example, critical skills thinking and functional skills were components of human progress on throughout its history and have found recognition of their importance in advances in applied, agricultural, medical and other research. Skills in acquiring a wide range of knowledge (from factual to complex analytical) are also are not new.

Truly new is the conclusion that the listed skills are significant outside the general pedagogical context and therefore the level of their development in specific subjects, as well as the collective of subjects, the dynamics of changes in the world economy is ultimately determined. In this regard, schools should be more consistent in teaching critical thinking to students, in a comprehensive solution to problems related to the individuality of each student. To implement such fundamental changes, it is necessary to making commitments to the leadership of schools and actively participating in their implementation most experienced and talented teachers, all stakeholders of the education system.

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